

Evaluating Hypertension and Diabetes Management as Tracer Indicators of Primary Healthcare System Performance and Readiness in Rural Ghana

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension (HTN) and diabetes (DM) are important indicators of primary healthcare system readiness, yet evidence from rural Ghana remains limited. This study assessed screening, diagnosis, treatment, and control of HTN and DM in five rural communities in Akatsi South District, Ghana. A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted among 507 adults aged 18–75 years using questionnaires, blood pressure measurements, and fasting blood glucose tests.

Blood pressure screening coverage was 79.5%, while hypertension prevalence was 20.9%. Only 9.3% reported antihypertensive use, and 71.7% of those with elevated blood pressure were unaware of their condition. Nearly half of diagnosed cases remained uncontrolled. Blood glucose testing coverage was 70.8%, with diabetes prevalence at 7.7%. However, only 12.7% were on treatment, and 76.9% of diabetes cases were previously undiagnosed. Overall, major gaps existed in detection, treatment, and long-term control of both conditions.

The findings indicate limited primary healthcare capacity for chronic disease management in rural Ghana and highlight low readiness of primary care systems to effectively address non-communicable diseases..

1. Introduction

Primary healthcare (PHC) is the cornerstone of equitable health systems, serving as the principal platform for delivering essential services and achieving population health gains, particularly in resource-constrained settings. Over the past decade, a substantial body of empirical evidence has demonstrated that robust PHC systems are associated with improved health outcomes, largely due to their wide population reach, relative affordability, integrated service delivery structures, and capacity to deploy contextually appropriate and socially acceptable interventions with meaningful community engagement.^{1 2} PHC is not only the first point of contact with the health system but also a key strategy for achieving universal health coverage and reducing health inequalities.

The importance of primary healthcare is even greater in the context of non-communicable diseases, which exhibit a different pattern from that of acute diseases. Unlike short-term illnesses, non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as diabetes and hypertension require long-term and continuous care. Effective management depends on a full continuum of services, including early detection, regular risk monitoring, lifestyle and behavior change support, psychosocial care, and sustained adherence to treatment over time.^{3 4} Within this continuum of

care, primary healthcare systems are well placed to ensure continuity of services because they are easily accessible and often serve as the first point of contact for patients. This ongoing relationship allows for regular follow-up, health education, and early treatment when problems arise. As a result, PHC provides a suitable and efficient platform for the prevention and control of non-communicable diseases.

Primary healthcare systems in Ghana, particularly in rural areas, like in many low- and middle-income countries, face major challenges that reduce access to essential health services. These challenges are largely driven by structural, socioeconomic, and geographic barriers. Evidence consistently shows that financial constraints, long distances to health facilities, and shortages of medicines and diagnostic equipment are key factors that limit effective disease management and timely care.^{5 6} In addition, limited numbers of trained health workers, unreliable supply of medicines and diagnostic tools, and poor implementation of clinical guidelines reduce the readiness of primary healthcare services.⁷ These health system challenges are further worsened by patient-related factors such as low health literacy, cultural beliefs, and poor adherence to treatment. These factors limit effective disease management and control at the primary care level.⁸ Evidence from rural districts also shows that

¹ Margaret E. Kruk et al., "High-Quality Health Systems in the Sustainable Development Goals Era: Time for a Revolution," *The Lancet Global Health* 6, no. 11 (November 2018): e1196–252, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(18\)30386-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(18)30386-3).

² Kara Hanson et al., "The Lancet Global Health Commission on Financing Primary Health Care: Putting People at the Centre," *The Lancet Global Health* 10, no. 5 (May 2022): e715–72, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X\(22\)00005-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2214-109X(22)00005-5).

³ Robert Beaglehole et al., "Priority Actions for the Non-Communicable Disease Crisis," *The Lancet* 377, no. 9775 (April 2011): 1438–47, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(11\)60393-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(11)60393-0).

⁴ World Health Organization, *Noncommunicable Diseases Progress Monitor 2020* (Geneva, 2020), <https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/ncd-progress-monitor-2020>.

⁵ Samuel Byiringiro et al., 'Healthcare System Barriers and Facilitators to Hypertension Management in Ghana', *Annals of Global Health* 90, no. 1 (2024): 38, <https://doi.org/10.5334/aogh.4246>.

⁶ Francis Sambah et al., 'A Qualitative Study on the Barriers and Enablers to Effective Hypertension Management in Ghana', *Healthcare* 13, no. 5 (2025): 479, <https://doi.org/10.3390/healthcare13050479>.

⁷ Samuel Byiringiro et al., 'Healthcare System Barriers and Facilitators to Hypertension Management in Ghana', *Annals of Global Health* 90, no. 1 (2024): 38, <https://doi.org/10.5334/aogh.4246>.

⁸ Sambah et al., 'A Qualitative Study on the Barriers and Enablers to Effective Hypertension Management in Ghana'.

socioeconomic factors, especially education level and income, strongly influence how people use healthcare services. This contributes to unequal access to care and differences in health outcomes, with disadvantaged groups experiencing poorer access and outcomes.⁹

Beyond access barriers, the “care cascade” helps explain where people are lost in managing hypertension and diabetes. At each step: screening, diagnosis, starting treatment, and long-term follow-up, many individuals drop out. As a result, a large number remain undiagnosed, untreated, or poorly controlled. Although some health facilities in Ghana are moderately prepared to provide NCD services, important gaps remain. These include limited diagnostic tools, shortages of health workers, and inconsistent availability of essential medicines and supplies.¹⁰ These gaps highlight the need for a more nuanced assessment of health system readiness that goes beyond service availability to encompass functionality, equity, and continuity of care.

Given the primary health system’s central role in managing chronic diseases, it is essential to understand how well these systems function in rural settings. In particular, there is a need to assess the extent to which primary healthcare facilities are prepared to provide effective services for non-communicable diseases. This is important because weak or poorly prepared systems can lead to delayed diagnosis, inadequate treatment, and ultimately worse health outcomes for people living with chronic conditions such as hypertension and diabetes.

This study therefore uses hypertension and diabetes as indicator conditions to assess how well the health system in

rural Ghana is prepared to detect, treat, and manage chronic diseases. These conditions provide a practical way to observe how well the health system performs across key stages of care, including screening, diagnosis, treatment, and long-term management. By bringing together evidence on barriers to access, socioeconomic conditions, and gaps along the care continuum, the study provides a clearer, more complete picture of how both system-level weaknesses and contextual factors influence NCD outcomes. This integrated understanding is essential for identifying where the health system is failing and why these gaps persist. It also provides a strong foundation for designing targeted, context-specific interventions that can strengthen primary healthcare services. Ultimately, improving system readiness is key to ensuring more equitable and effective chronic disease care for underserved rural populations.

2. Methodology

The author employed a population-based, descriptive cross-sectional design using quantitative methods. The research was conducted across five strategically purposively selected remote rural villages within the Akatsi South District of the Volta Region, Ghana: Ayiti Korpe, Gefia, Atidzive, Lume Avete, and Torve. A two-stage cluster sampling approach was used: the five villages were purposively selected as clusters, and households within each village were systematically selected at fixed intervals. One adult per household was randomly selected. This population-based study included 507 adults aged 18-75 years who were permanent residents (≥ 6 months), encompassing both genders and all hypertension/diabetes cases (diagnosed and undiagnosed) to capture the true

⁹ Mercy N. A. Opare-Addo et al., ‘Healthcare Services Utilisation among Patients with Hypertension and Diabetes in Rural Ghana’, *African Journal of Primary Health Care & Family Medicine* 12, no. 1 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.4102/phcfm.v12i1.2114>.

¹⁰ Thomas Hinneh et al., ‘Health Services Availability and Readiness for Management of Hypertension and Diabetes in Primary Care Health Facilities in Ghana: A Cardiovascular Risk Management Project’, *Global Heart* 19, no. 1 (2024): 92, <https://doi.org/10.5334/gh.1375>.

epidemiological burden, while excluding pregnant women, visitors under 18, and those unable to consent due to cognitive impairment or severe illness.

First, the initial sample size for an infinite population was calculated using the formula:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot p \cdot (1 - p)}{E^2}$$

where:

Z = Z-score for desired confidence level (for 95%, Z=1.96)

p = prevalence in population (0.5)

E = desired margin of error (d=0.05)

After applying the finite population correction, the required sample size was 357 (confirmed using Epi Info™ StatCalc), but 507 participants were recruited, improving precision and reducing the margin of error to below 5% at 95% confidence, ensuring robust, well-powered estimates.

The main outcomes were the prevalence of hypertension and diabetes.

Hypertension was defined according to the World Health Organization criteria as systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg, or current use of antihypertensive medication. Severe hypertension was defined as blood pressure $\geq 160/100$ mmHg, or uncontrolled blood pressure among individuals already on treatment.¹¹

Additional indicators included whether individuals had ever had their blood pressure measured by a health professional (screening), had previously been told they had hypertension

(awareness), had a recent check within the past 12 months, were currently on treatment, or were using traditional or herbal therapies.

Diabetes was defined as fasting blood glucose ≥ 7.0 mmol/L after at least 8 hours of fasting, or current use of antidiabetic medication. Prediabetes was defined as fasting blood glucose between 6.1 and 6.9 mmol/L.¹² Other indicators included prior blood glucose testing (screening), prior diagnosis (awareness), recent confirmation within the past 12 months, current treatment, and use of traditional remedies.

These measures were used to build care cascades for both conditions, showing the progression from disease prevalence to screening and awareness, treatment uptake, and effective control. Control was defined as blood pressure $< 140/90$ mmHg for hypertension and fasting blood glucose < 7.0 mmol/L for diabetes among those on treatment.

Sociodemographic variables included age (18-29, 30-44, 45-59, and 60-75 years), sex, education level, marital status, occupation, and main source of income. Household characteristics were used to reflect broader social determinants of health and included household size, food insecurity in the past 12 months, and patterns of agricultural production.

Healthcare access was assessed using distance to the nearest health facility, use of healthcare services in the past 12 months, and perceived barriers to care, especially financial constraints and trust in formal healthcare. Family history of hypertension or diabetes was also recorded, although many participants were unsure of their family history.

¹¹ World Health Organization, "Hypertension," accessed April 30, 2026, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/hypertension>.

¹² Eleanor Barry et al., "Efficacy and Effectiveness of Screen and Treat Policies in Prevention of Type 2 Diabetes: Systematic Review and Meta-

Analysis of Screening Tests and Interventions," *BMJ*, January 4, 2017, i6538, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.i6538>.

Clinical variables included body mass index (BMI), categorized using standard cut-offs (underweight <18.5 kg/m², overweight 25-29.9 kg/m², and obese ≥ 30 kg/m²),¹³ resting heart rate, and average systolic and diastolic blood pressure. Behavioral and contextual factors, such as the use of traditional remedies, were included to capture local health practices and related risk factors.

Data were collected using pre-tested structured questionnaires administered through face-to-face interviews. Internal reliability of composite scales (e.g., knowledge and attitudes) was assessed using Cronbach's alpha, with values above $\alpha > 0.70$ indicating acceptable consistency. Items with low item-total correlations were reviewed or removed to ensure that each scale measured a single concept. Inter-rater reliability was maintained through thorough training of fieldworkers and regular calibration exercises to ensure consistent anthropometric measurements and standardized questionnaire administration.

Clinical measurements followed standard procedures. Blood pressure was measured with an Omron M3 digital device, taking three readings per participant and using the average of the last two for analysis. Fasting blood glucose was measured using an Accu-Chek Instant point-of-care device.

Height and weight were measured with participants wearing light clothing and no shoes, using a portable stadiometer and a calibrated digital scale. Height was recorded to the nearest 0.1 cm and weight to the nearest 0.1 kg. BMI was calculated as weight (kg) divided by height squared (m²) and used as the main measure of body fat in the analysis.

Descriptive analyses were used to describe the study population and estimate the burden of disease. Categorical variables were summarized as frequencies and percentages, with 95% confidence intervals calculated using the Wilson method. Continuous variables were summarized using means and standard deviations or medians and interquartile ranges, depending on the data distribution.

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was employed to assess mean differences across age categories when the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variances were reasonably met. Levene's test for homogeneity of variances was applied to evaluate the equality of variances across groups. Where Levene's test indicated violation of the homogeneity assumption ($p < .05$), results were interpreted with caution, and robustness considerations were applied. For variables where the ANOVA assumptions were not fully met, particularly when distributions were non-normal, or variances were unequal, the Kruskal-Wallis H test, a nonparametric alternative to ANOVA, was used to compare median differences across age groups. All statistical tests were two-tailed, and a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ was adopted. Results were interpreted as statistically significant when p-values were less than 0.05. Statistical analyses were stratified by sex to account for potential biological differences in cardiovascular risk profiles.

All analyses were conducted using SPSS version 27 and Epi Info version 7. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ghana Health Service (regional and district health directorates) and the EUCLID

¹³ World Health Organization, "Obesity and Overweight," accessed May 1, 2026, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight>.

University Ethical Committee (EC/2024/1129). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

3. Findings

3.1. Age and gender distribution of the study population

The study included 507 adults aged 18-75 years from five remote rural communities in Akatsi South District, Volta Region, Ghana. Participants comprised 233 men (46%) and 274 women (54%). (Table 1)

Blood Pressure Screening and Management

3.2. Percentage of individuals with current elevated BP who were not previously diagnosed (i.e., proportion of measured hypertension that is newly detected / undiagnosed)

Overall, 71.7% (95% CI: 62.5-79.3) of participants with hypertension were not previously aware of their condition and were newly identified during this survey. Undiagnosed hypertension remained high across most age groups and in both sexes. This indicates that about 3 in 4 people with hypertension in this population were unaware of their condition. (Tables 3 & 5)

3.3. Percentage of adults with previously diagnosed hypertension who are currently on antihypertensive medication (i.e., treatment coverage among known cases)

Only 31.1% (95% CI: 23.0-40.5%) of individuals with hypertension are currently on antihypertensive medication. Treatment coverage is very low across all age groups and in both sexes, including older adults, where it still does not exceed 38%. There is no meaningful difference between men (31.9%) and women (30.4%). This indicates that about 7 out of every 10 people with hypertension are not receiving any medication, showing a major treatment gap. When considered together with the high level of undiagnosed cases (71.7%), the findings highlight both poor detection and poor treatment of

hypertension in the sampled population. Overall, only about 1 in 10 adults who need treatment (those with elevated blood pressure) are actually receiving antihypertensive medication. (Tables 3 & 5)

3.4. Percentage of previously diagnosed hypertension cases who are on medication but still have elevated BP at the time of survey (i.e., treated but uncontrolled)

About 46.9% (95% CI: 30.9-63.6) of individuals on treatment still have uncontrolled hypertension (blood pressure $\geq 140/90$ mmHg). Control is especially poor among older adults, with about 64% of treated people aged 60-75 years remaining uncontrolled, and among men, where 53% of those on treatment are uncontrolled. In simple terms, fewer than half of people who know they have hypertension and are taking medication have their blood pressure well controlled. Overall, hypertension control in this population is very poor, with fewer than 1 in 20 people with hypertension achieving adequate control. (Table 3 & 5)

3.5. Respondents who have ever had their blood pressure measured by a health professional

Most participants reported having been screened for blood pressure before. Overall, 79.5% (95% CI: 75.8-82.8) had ever had their blood pressure measured, while 20.5% had never been screened (Tables 3 & 5).

3.6. Respondents who see a traditional healer/complementary medicine practitioner for elevated blood pressure among the whole adult population

Overall, 13.0% of adults (95% CI: 10.3-16.2) reported ever consulting a traditional healer or complementary/alternative medicine practitioner for high blood pressure. This practice was more common among women than men (15.7% vs 9.4%; $p < 0.05$). Use increased with age: it was rare among young adults (<5% in those aged 18-9 years), rose to about 16-20% among

adults aged 45 years and above, and was highest among women aged 60-75 years (23.2%).

3.7. Respondents who are currently taking herbal or traditional remedies for raised blood pressure among the whole adult population

13.4% of all adults (95% CI: 10.7-16.7%) report currently using herbal or traditional remedies for high blood pressure. Use is almost twice as common in women (16.8%) compared with men (9.0%), and this difference is statistically significant ($p < 0.01$). Use of traditional or herbal remedies increases with age. It is very low among young adults (below 2.5% in those aged 18-29 years), but rises markedly in older age groups, reaching about 22% overall in older adults and 29% among women aged 60-75 years.

3.8. Respondents who do not know whether they have a family history of high blood pressure "Don't Know" response.

Almost 60% of adults (95% CI 55.3-63.7) do not know whether anyone in their family has (or had) high blood pressure.

Blood Sugar Screening and Management

3.9. Percentage of individuals with current elevated FBS (diabetes range) who were not previously diagnosed (i.e., proportion of measured diabetes that is newly detected)

About 76.9% (95% CI: 61.7-87.4%) of individuals with diabetes were not previously diagnosed, meaning their condition was identified for the first time during this survey. Undiagnosed diabetes was consistently high across all age and sex groups, ranging from 71% to 100%, with no meaningful difference between men (75.0%) and women (80.0%). This indicates that roughly 3 out of every 4 people with blood sugar levels in the diabetic range are unaware that they have diabetes. Only 23.1% (95% CI: 12.8-38.3%) had prior knowledge of their condition, meaning they had already been told they have elevated blood sugar or diabetes (Tables 4 & 5).

3.10. Percentage of adults with previously diagnosed diabetes who are currently on medication (i.e., treatment coverage among known diabetes cases)

Only 12.7% (95% CI: 6.8-22.3) of individuals with diabetes are currently on glucose-lowering medication. Treatment coverage among those already diagnosed is very low across all age and sex groups, and does not exceed 44% in any subgroup, dropping to as low as 0-7% in most older age groups. Men are somewhat more likely to be treated than women (19.4% vs 7.5%), but overall treatment levels remain very poor in both groups. In practical terms, this means that about 9 out of 10 people (87.3%) who already know they have diabetes are not receiving any medication to control their blood sugar. This indicates a major treatment gap even among diagnosed cases. When this is considered together with the very high proportion of undiagnosed diabetes (76.9%), it shows a severely broken diabetes care cascade in this population, with major gaps in both diagnosis and treatment. (Tables 4 & 5)

3.11. Percentage of previously diagnosed diabetes cases who are on medication but still have elevated fasting blood sugar (≥ 7.0 mmol/l) at the time of survey (i.e., treated but uncontrolled diabetes)

Among individuals who were previously diagnosed with diabetes and reported being on medication, 100% still had elevated fasting blood glucose (≥ 7.0 mmol/L) at the time of the survey. This shows that there is no glycaemic control among the small number of treated cases in this population. This pattern suggests possible poor treatment effectiveness and/or poor medication adherence. It may also reflect the use of inadequate or non-evidence-based treatments, including reliance on herbal remedies, as well as the possibility of advanced disease requiring more intensive management. Overall, none of the known and treated individuals had controlled diabetes at the time of assessment (Tables 4 & 5).

3.12. *Respondents who have ever had their blood sugar measured by a health professional*

70.8% of adults reported ever having their blood sugar measured (95% CI: 66.7-74.6), while 29.2% (95% CI: 25.4-33.3) had never been tested. This indicates that nearly one in three adults has never been screened for abnormal blood glucose (dysglycaemia), highlighting a substantial gap in diabetes screening coverage in the population (Tables 4 & 5).

3.13. *Respondents who do not know whether they have a family history of high blood sugar / diabetes "Don't Know" response*

Nearly two-thirds of adults (64.1%; 95% CI 59.9-68.2%) do not know whether anyone in their family has (or had) high blood sugar or diabetes. Ignorance is highest among young adults (73% in the 18-29 age group) and remains above 65% through age 59. Only 14.7% of all adults (95% CI 11.9-18.1) are aware of a positive family history of high blood sugar or diabetes. (Table 4 & 5)

Health Access Barriers and Socioeconomic Status

3.14. *Mean distance to the nearest chief compound clinic*

The average distance to the nearest Community-based Health Planning and Services (CHPS) facility in these remote rural communities was 2.75 km (SD 1.50). However, this relatively close physical access did not lead to high service use, mainly because these CHPS compounds functioned more as basic first-aid points and lacked adequate equipment and services. The average self-reported distance to the nearest district clinic was 4.55 km (SD 3.60) (Table 2).

3.15. *Respondents' main barrier to healthcare*

Financial barriers were the main obstacle to accessing healthcare in this group. About 60.8% of respondents (95% CI: 56.4-64.9) reported that cost prevented them from seeking care, making it the most common barrier. Other barriers, such as cultural beliefs, lack of trust in healthcare providers, long distances to facilities, and transport difficulties, were reported less frequently and, together, accounted for a smaller proportion of responses (Table 2).

3.16. *Respondents' main source of income*

Farming was the predominant source of income, reported by 81.8% of participants (95% CI: 78.1-84.9). Trading was the next most frequent source, cited by 7.1% (95% CI: 5.2-9.7). The average household size in the sample was 5.1 persons (SD = 2.4; range, 1-20).

4. Discussion

The study uses hypertension and diabetes as indicator conditions to assess how well rural primary healthcare in Ghana is functioning. The findings show that while the system can detect these conditions to some extent, it is not well-equipped to provide ongoing, continuous care. This gap between diagnosis and long-term management reflects weaknesses in health financing, service delivery, and how the health workforce is organized.

The observed hypertension prevalence confirms that rural Ghana has entered an advanced stage of epidemiological transition, consistent with national estimates and comparable to rural populations in East Africa.^{14 15} Similarly, the diabetes prevalence alongside a substantial burden of impaired fasting

¹⁴ Feven Ataklte et al., "Burden of Undiagnosed Hypertension in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis," *Hypertension* 65, no. 2 (February 2015): 291-98, <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.114.04394>.

¹⁵ Ghana Health Service, *GHANA STEPS REPORT 2023: NATIONWIDE NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASES RISK FACTORS ASSESSMENT USING THE WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION'S STEPWISE APPROACH IN GHANA* (Accra: GHS Press, 2024), file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/ghana-2023-steps-report.pdf.

glucose aligns with emerging sub-Saharan African trends reported in countries such as Kenya and Tanzania.^{16 17 18} These patterns show that NCDs are no longer mainly an urban problem. Instead, they are becoming common across both rural and urban areas due to population aging, dietary changes, and lower levels of physical activity.

However, the key implication for PHC readiness lies not in prevalence alone but in the pronounced breakdown across the care cascade. Over 70% of individuals with hypertension and approximately 77% of those with diabetes were previously undiagnosed, mirroring findings from WHO STEPS surveys and other Ghanaian studies.^{19 20} This persistent diagnostic gap underscores a fundamental failure in primary prevention capacity. While Ghana's Community-Based Health Planning and Services model has improved geographic access, it has not systematically integrated routine NCD screening into its core service package. In contrast, countries such as Rwanda and Ethiopia have demonstrated that embedding hypertension and diabetes screening into community health worker programs can significantly improve early detection and awareness.²¹

Even more revealing of system readiness are the findings on treatment and control. Only 31% of individuals aware of their hypertension were on treatment, and fewer than 5% achieved effective control. For diabetes, treatment coverage was even lower, with negligible levels of glycemic control. These outcomes are consistent with regional estimates showing that less than 10% of hypertensive patients in sub-Saharan Africa achieve adequate control,²² but they also highlight the structural drivers of this failure. Unlike high-income settings, where treatment and control rates often exceed 50-60%, the Ghanaian PHC system lacks the continuity mechanisms necessary for chronic care, including reliable drug supply chains, patient tracking systems, and regular follow-up protocols.

Financial barriers emerge as a central constraint shaping these outcomes. Although the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) has expanded coverage, this study demonstrates that insurance enrollment does not equate to effective access. Persistent medication stockouts, delayed reimbursements, and out-of-pocket expenditures for diagnostics and drugs undermine adherence and continuity of care. Similar findings have been reported in Ghana and Nigeria, where health insurance schemes have limited impact on chronic disease

¹⁶ Shukri F. Mohamed et al., "Prevalence, Awareness, Treatment and Control of Hypertension and Their Determinants: Results from a National Survey in Kenya," *BMC Public Health* 18, no. S3 (November 2018): 1219, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-018-6052-y>.

¹⁷ Brianna Osetinsky et al., "Care Cascades for Hypertension and Diabetes: Cross-Sectional Evaluation of Rural Districts in Tanzania," *PLOS Medicine* 19, no. 12 (December 2022): e1004140, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.1004140>.

¹⁸ Ibrahim Franklyn Kamara et al., "Prevalence of Hypertension, Diabetes Mellitus, and Their Risk Factors in an Informal Settlement in Freetown, Sierra Leone: A Cross-Sectional Study," *BMC Public Health* 24, no. 1 (March 2024): 783, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-18158-w>.

¹⁹ Thomas Hinneh et al., "Prevalence of Suboptimal Blood Pressure, Glycemic Control, and Associated Factors among Patients with Diabetes and

Hypertension in Primary Health Care Facilities in Ghana: A Multicenter Retrospective Cross-Sectional Study," *BMC Primary Care* 26, no. 1 (May 2025): 189, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12875-025-02775-4>.

²⁰ Ashraful Kabir et al., "Health System Readiness for Non-Communicable Diseases at the Primary Care Level: A Systematic Review," *BMJ Open* 12, no. 2 (February 2022): e060387, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2021-060387>.

²¹ Yohannes Mekuria Negussie and Abel Tezera Abebe, "Hypertension and Associated Factors among Patients with Diabetes Mellitus Attending a Follow-up Clinic in Central Ethiopia," *Scientific Reports* 15, no. 1 (April 2025): 13150, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-97909-0>.

²² Feven Ataklte et al., "Burden of Undiagnosed Hypertension in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis," *Hypertension* 65, no. 2 (February 2015): 291-98, <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.114.04394>.

management due to systemic inefficiencies.^{23 24} In contrast, Thailand's Universal Coverage Scheme illustrates how comprehensive inclusion of NCD services, including medications and routine monitoring, can substantially improve control rates and reduce catastrophic health expenditure.²⁵

The coexistence of relatively high hypertension screening with low treatment uptake and poor disease control highlights a major gap in primary healthcare delivery. In rural Ghana, screening is mainly done through occasional outreach campaigns rather than as part of routine, continuous preventive care across the life course. A similar pattern is seen in many low- and middle-income countries, where short-term, campaign-based screening improves case detection but does not ensure sustained follow-up and long-term management.²⁶ The lack of integrated chronic care systems, as recommended in the WHO Package of Essential NCD Interventions, limits primary healthcare services' ability to shift from short-term, one-off treatment to ongoing, continuous care for chronic diseases. Socioeconomic and structural factors also worsen these gaps.²⁷ Poverty, farming-based livelihoods, and unstable seasonal incomes make it harder for people to consistently use healthcare services. At the same time, food insecurity and changing diets increase the risk of metabolic conditions such as diabetes and hypertension. These findings are consistent

with evidence from rural Africa, where both economic hardship and weak health system capacity contribute to poor outcomes for non-communicable diseases. Importantly, the study shows that living close to a health facility does not necessarily mean people can effectively access care. Real access depends not only on distance, but also on affordability, service quality, and whether health facilities are properly equipped to provide ongoing NCD care.

From a policy perspective, the findings are clear. The management of hypertension and diabetes shows that Ghana's primary healthcare system is still largely focused on acute and communicable diseases, with limited capacity for long-term chronic disease care. Improving PHC readiness will require a shift toward integrated chronic care models. This includes regular community-based screening, consistent availability of essential medicines, task-shifting to trained nurses and community health workers, and aligning National Health Insurance Scheme financing with the long-term care needs of people living with non-communicable diseases.

In conclusion, hypertension and diabetes serve as key indicators of the functioning of the primary healthcare system in rural Ghana. The ongoing gaps in awareness, treatment, and control reflect not only clinical problems but also deeper weaknesses in the health system. Improving this situation will require coordinated changes in financing, service delivery, and

²³ Abigail Nyarko Codjoe Derkyi-Kwarteng et al., "A Narrative Synthesis Review of Out-of-Pocket Payments for Health Services Under Insurance Regimes: A Policy Implementation Gap Hindering Universal Health Coverage in Sub-Saharan Africa," *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, May 1, 2021, 1, <https://doi.org/10.34172/ijhpm.2021.38>.

²⁴ Robert Kaba Alhassan, Edward Nketiah-Amponsah, and Daniel Kojo Arhinful, "A Review of the National Health Insurance Scheme in Ghana: What Are the Sustainability Threats and Prospects?," *PLOS ONE* 11, no. 11 (November 2016): e0165151, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0165151>.

²⁵ Viroj Tangcharoensathien et al., "Health Systems Development in Thailand: A Solid Platform for Successful Implementation of Universal Health

Coverage," *The Lancet* 391, no. 10126 (March 2018): 1205–23, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)30198-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)30198-3).

²⁶ S. Ebrahim, "Chronic Diseases and Calls to Action," *International Journal of Epidemiology* 37, no. 2 (April 2008): 225–30, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyn016>.

²⁷ Ahmed Hassan Albelbeisi et al., "Public Sector Capacity to Prevent and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases in Twelve Low- and Middle-Income Countries Based on WHO-PEN Standards: A Systematic Review," *Health Services Insights* 14 (January 2021): 1178632920986233, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1178632920986233>.

community involvement to ensure PHC services can effectively manage the growing burden of non-communicable diseases.

The limitation of this study is that health system readiness was inferred from population-level experience rather than direct facility assessment. As a result, the study does not directly measure staffing, equipment, stock status, or facility-level readiness inputs.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study shows that hypertension and diabetes are two major chronic diseases that reveal a key weakness in rural Ghana's primary healthcare system. While the system can detect these conditions through screening, it is weak in providing continuous, long-term care. There is a clear drop-off from diagnosis to sustained treatment and disease control, showing a fragmented care pathway. To improve care, primary healthcare should shift to simple, integrated, and continuous chronic disease management.

For hypertension, blood pressure should be checked at every primary healthcare/CHPS contact, with proper recording in a shared NCD register. Community outreach screening should be done regularly. Treatment should use simple once-daily or fixed-dose drug combinations, with reliable medicine supply through the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) and CHPS facilities. Patient adherence can be improved through community support groups and routine monitoring of traditional medicine use and family risk.

For diabetes, screening should focus on adults aged 40 years and above and other high-risk groups, using simple risk screening tools where needed. Treatment should follow stepwise guidelines, with at least one essential diabetes medicine always available at the primary care level. Patients

should be followed up every 3-6 months, and community education should improve awareness and encourage household-level screening.

6. Conflict of Interest

The author states that there is no conflict of interest.

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Table 1: Sociodemographic And Household Characteristics of Respondents

Characteristic	Category	N	%
Sex	Men	233	46.0
	Women	274	54.0
Age group (years)	18-29	84	16.6
	30-44	117	23.1
	45-59	179	35.3
	60-75	127	25.1
Educational level	No formal education	131	25.8
	Primary	241	47.5
	Secondary	115	22.7
	Tertiary	20	3.9
Occupation	Farming	330	65.1
	Trading	88	17.4
	No occupation	33	6.5

Characteristic	Category	N	%
Marital status	Other occupations	56	11.1
	Married	330	65.1
	Single	60	11.8
	Divorced	57	11.2
Religion	Widowed	60	11.8
	Christian	372	73.4
	None	104	20.5
	Traditionalist	16	3.2
	Muslim	15	3.0

Note. Data are presented as frequencies (N) and percentages (%). Percentages may not sum to 100 due to rounding. N represents the number of respondents with available data for each characteristic. Educational level refers to the highest level of formal education attained. Occupation categories are self-reported main livelihood activities

Table 2: Health-seeking, Access Barriers, and Socioeconomic Context in the Study Population

Indicator	n / Mean	% / SD
Visited a doctor in the past 12 months	225	44.6
Did not visit a doctor in the past 12 months	280	55.4
Ever had blood pressure measured	403	79.5

Indicator	n / Mean	% / SD
Ever had blood sugar measured	359	70.8
Main barrier to healthcare: cost	308	60.8
Main barrier to healthcare: lack of trust in providers	41	8.1
Main barrier to healthcare: cultural beliefs	15	3.0
Main barrier to healthcare: distance	5	1.0
Main barrier to healthcare: transportation	2	0.4
Mean distance to nearest CHPS (km)	2.75	(SD = 1.5)
Mean distance to nearest district hospital (km)	4.55	(SD = 3.6)
Main source of income: farming	412	81.8
Household food insecurity in past 12 months	110	21.7
Mean household size	5.1	(SD = 2.4)

Note. Values are presented as frequency (n), percentage (%), or mean with standard deviation (SD), as appropriate. Percentages may not sum to 100% due to rounding. "Visited a doctor" refers to any outpatient consultation within the past 12 months. "Ever had blood pressure/blood sugar measured" refers to lifetime screening history. Distances are reported in kilometers (km) to the nearest primary health care facility (CHPS compound) and district hospital, respectively. Household food insecurity refers to any reported experience of food shortage within the past 12 months. Multiple responses were allowed for reported barriers to healthcare access; therefore, categories are not mutually exclusive.

Table 3: Hypertension Care Continuum Cascade

Cascade step	n	%	95% CI
Elevated blood pressure ($\geq 140/90$ mmHg or on treatment)	106	20.9	17.6- 24.7
Severe elevated blood pressure ($\geq 160/100$ mmHg or on treatment with BP still $\geq 160/100$ mmHg)	34	6.7	4.8- 9.2
Previously diagnosed hypertension	103	20.3	17.0- 24.0
Undiagnosed among current hypertension cases	76	71.7	62.5- 79.3
Previously aware among current hypertension cases	30	28.3	20.7- 37.5
Currently on antihypertensive medication among known cases	32	31.1	23.0- 40.5
Uncontrolled among treated cases	15	46.9	30.9- 63.6
Controlled among treated cases	17	53.1	36.4- 69.1

Note. Values are presented as number (n), percentage (%), and 95% confidence interval (CI). Elevated blood pressure was defined as systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 mmHg or current use of antihypertensive medication. Severe elevated blood pressure was defined as systolic blood pressure ≥ 160 mmHg and/or diastolic blood pressure ≥ 100 mmHg or current antihypertensive treatment with blood pressure still $\geq 160/100$ mmHg. “Previously diagnosed hypertension” refers to self-reported prior medical diagnosis of hypertension. “Undiagnosed among current hypertension cases” represents individuals with elevated blood pressure who had no prior diagnosis. “Previously aware among current hypertension cases” includes individuals who reported prior awareness of their hypertensive status. “Currently on antihypertensive medication among known cases” refers to participants reporting current treatment among those previously diagnosed. Blood pressure control status was assessed among those on treatment, with controlled defined as blood pressure $< 140/90$ mmHg and uncontrolled defined as blood pressure $\geq 140/90$ mmHg.

Table 4: Diabetes Care Continuum Cascade

Cascade step	n	%	95% CI
Diabetes-range fasting blood sugar (≥ 7.0 mmol/L or on medication)	39	7.7	5.7-10.3
Impaired fasting blood sugar (6.1–6.9 mmol/L)	55	10.8	8.4-13.9
Previously diagnosed diabetes	71	14.0	11.3-17.3
Undiagnosed among current diabetes cases	30	76.9	61.7-87.4
Previously aware among current diabetes cases	9	23.1	12.8-38.3
Currently on diabetes medication among known cases	9	12.7	6.8-22.3
Uncontrolled among treated cases	9	100.0	66.4-100.0
Controlled among treated cases	0	0.0	0.0-33.6

Note. *n* = number of respondents; % = percentage of respondents within each cascade category; CI = confidence interval. Diabetes-range fasting blood sugar defined as fasting blood glucose ≥ 7.0 mmol/L or current use of diabetes medication. Impaired fasting blood sugar defined as fasting blood glucose 6.1–6.9 mmol/L. Previously diagnosed diabetes refers to self-reported prior medical diagnosis of diabetes. Undiagnosed cases represent participants with diabetes-range fasting blood sugar who had no prior diagnosis. Previously aware cases refer to respondents reporting prior knowledge of their diabetic status. Currently on diabetes medication includes respondents reporting current pharmacological treatment for diabetes. Uncontrolled among treated cases refers to those on medication but with fasting blood glucose ≥ 7.0 mmol/L at survey time. Controlled among treated cases refers to those on medication with fasting blood glucose below diagnostic threshold.

Table 5: Summary of Health System Readiness Indicators for Hypertension and Diabetes Control in Rural Ghana: Access, Screening, and Care Cascade Summary

Domain	Indicator	Result (95% CI)
Access	Ever visited doctor in past 12 months	44.6% (40.3-48.9)
Access	Main barrier to care (Cost)	(60.8%; 56.4-64.9)
Screening	Ever had BP measured	79.5% (75.8-82.8)
Screening	Ever had blood sugar measured	70.8% (66.7-74.6)
Hypertension burden	Elevated blood pressure	20.9% (17.6-24.7)
Hypertension cascade	Awareness among cases	28.3% (20.7-37.5)
Hypertension cascade	Treatment among known cases	31.1% (23.0-40.5)
Hypertension cascade	Control among treated cases	53.1% (36.4-69.1)
Diabetes burden	Diabetes-range fasting blood sugar	7.7% (5.7-10.3)
Diabetes cascade	Awareness among cases	23.1% (12.8-38.3)
Diabetes cascade	Treatment among known cases	12.7% (6.8-22.3)
Diabetes cascade	Control among treated cases	0.0% (0.0-33.6)
Household context	Food insecurity	21.7% (18.3-25.5)
Household context	Farming as main income	81.8% (78.1-84.9)

Note. BP = blood pressure. Percentages reflect population prevalence unless otherwise specified (e.g., “among cases” or “among known cases”). Confidence intervals calculated using Wilson method for proportions. This table provides a high-impact overview of health system performance gaps for hypertension and diabetes management in remote rural Ghana.

Table 6: Summary; Health System Care Continuum Gaps for Hypertension and Diabetes Management in Rural Ghana

Care continuum stage	Hypertension gap (%)	95% CI	Diabetes gap (%)	95% CI
Never screened	20.5	17.2-24.2	29.2	25.4-33.3
Undiagnosed cases	71.7	62.5-79.3	76.9	61.7-87.4
Untreated diagnosed	68.9	59.5-77.0	87.3	77.7-93.2
Uncontrolled treated	46.9	30.9-63.6	100.0	66.4-100.0
Dominant failure point	Detection & treatment		All stages	

Note. Values are presented as percentages (%) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) in parentheses. The hypertension and diabetes care continuum shows substantial attrition across all stages, with the highest gaps observed among undiagnosed and untreated diagnosed cases. The dominant failure points differ by condition, occurring primarily at the detection and treatment stages for hypertension, whereas diabetes shows pervasive system-wide failures across all stages of care.